

A Bibliometric Overview of the International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence

Hugo Baier-Fuentes¹, Jesús Cascón-Katchadourian², M.A Martínez³, Enrique Herrera-Viedma⁴, José M. Merigó^{5,6} *

¹ Department of Business Administration, Universidad Católica de la Santísima Concepción. Av. Alonso de Ribera 2850, Concepción (Chile)

² Department of Information and Communication. Faculty of Communication and Documentation. Colegio Máximo de Cartuja, 18071, Granada (Spain)

³ Department of Social Work and Social Services, University of Granada, Granada (Spain)

⁴ Department of Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence, University of Granada, Av. Periodista Daniel Saucedo s/n, Granada, (Spain)

⁵ School of Systems, Management and Leadership, Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology, University of Technology Sydney, 81 Broadway, Ultimo, 2007 NSW (Australia)

⁶ Department of Management Control and Information Systems, School of Economics and Business, University of Chile, Av. Diagonal Paraguay 257, 8330015 Santiago (Chile)

Received 20 November 2018 | Accepted 28 November 2018 | Published 1 December 2018

ABSTRACT

The International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence (IJIMAI) published its first issue ten years ago. Currently, IJIMAI is indexed in the important database Emerging Sources Citation Index. This paper aims to identify, through a mapping of science, those most relevant aspects of the structure of publications made during the first 10 years of IJIMAI. Using VOSviewer software, the structural maps of the IJIMAI publications are analysed according to techniques such as bibliographic coupling, co-citations and co-occurrence of keywords. In addition, the evolution of the publications, citations and an analysis of the most cited papers of the journal are presented. The results show that IJIMAI has experienced a remarkable growth of both publications and citations in the last five years. We also observe that IJIMAI does not only capture the attention of the Spanish scientific community, but also of emerging countries such as India and Iran and emerging Latin American countries such as Colombia. With a such increasing behaviour, it is expected in the coming years that IJIMAI will position itself among the best journals with similar scientific scope.

KEYWORDS

Bibliometrics, Web Of Science, VOS Viewer.

DOI: 10.9781/ijimai.2018.12.003

I. INTRODUCTION

As stated in its access platform, the International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence (IJIMAI hereinafter), pretends to be an open access point to relevant research on advances in Artificial Intelligence tools or tools that use Artificial Intelligence with interactive multimedia techniques. IJIMAI published its first issue in December 2008, under the direction of its editors, Dr. Jesús Soto Carrión and Dr. Elisa García Gordo. This issue published research from diverse areas of knowledge, such as Medical Diagnosis, Semantic Metadata, Nature Conservancy and Intelligence perception. Until 2011, IJIMAI kept publishing an annual number. The period 2012 published 3 issues and finally, since 2013, it has kept publishing

4 issues per year. The year 2015 was specially important since the journal was indexed in the *Emerging Sources Citation Index* (ESCI hereinafter), considered an important database in the *Web of Science* (WoS hereinafter).

In 2018, IJIMAI celebrates its tenth anniversary, which stimulated our interest in carrying out a bibliometric analysis of all the publications made by the journal. According to Cobo et al. [1], Bibliometrics is a set of methods used to study the impact of a particular field, the impact of a set of researchers or a particular article. Among the main methods used in a Bibliometrics is performance analysis and science mapping [2]. The first one focuses on assessing the impact of scientific actors on a bibliographic database. Keep in mind that scientific actors involve countries, universities, departments, researchers. On the other hand, science mapping intended to show the structural and dynamic aspects of a field of research using techniques such as bibliographic coupling [3], the co-citations of documents [4], citation, co-authorship or co-occurrence of keywords. In line with the above, we want to emphasize that the objective of this contribution is to identify, through a science mapping the most relevant structural aspects of the publications made in IJIMAI. For this, this study uses the VOSviewer Software [5].

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: hbaier@ucsc.cl (Baier-Fuentes), jesuscacon@gmail.com (Cascón-Katchadourian), mundodesilencio@ugr.es (Martínez), viedma@decsai.ugr.es (Herrera-Viedma), jmerigo@fen.uchile.cl (Merigó).

- [14] Cobo, M.J., Martínez, M.A., Gutiérrez-Salcedo, M., Fujita, H., Herrera-Viedma, E., 2015. 25 years at Knowledge-Based Systems: A bibliometric analysis. *Knowledge-Based Systems* 80, 3–13.
- [15] Biemans, W., Griffin, A., Moenaert, R., 2007. Twenty Years of the Journal of Product Innovation Management: History, Participants, and Knowledge Stock and Flows. *The Journal of Product Innovation Management* 24, 193–213.
- [16] Gaviria-Marín, M., Merigó, J.M., Popa, S. 2018. Twenty years of the Journal of Knowledge Management: A bibliometric analysis, *Journal of Knowledge Management* 22, 1655-1687.
- [17] Cancino, C., Merigó, J.M., Coronado, F., Dessouky, Y., Dessouky, M. 2017. Forty years of Computers & Industrial Engineering: A bibliometric analysis. *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 113, 614–629.
- [18] Merigó, J.M., Cobo, M.J., Laengle, S., Rivas, D., Herrera-Viedma, E., 2018. Twenty years of Soft Computing: a bibliometric overview. *Soft Computing* In Press. doi:10.1007/s00500-018-3168-z.
- [19] Pritchard, A., 1969. Statistical Bibliography or Bibliometrics? *Journal of Documentation* 25, 348–349.
- [20] Small, H., 1999. Visualizing science by citation mapping. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science* 50, 799–813.
- [21] Morris, S.A., Van der Veer Martens, B., 2009. Mapping research specialties. *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology* 42, 213–295.
- [22] Cobo, M.J., López-Herrera, A.G., Herrera-Viedma, E., Herrera, F., 2011. Science mapping software tools: Review, analysis, and cooperative study among tools. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology* 62, 1382–1402.
- [23] Chen, C., 2006. CiteSpace II: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology* 57, 359–377.
- [24] Persson, O., Danell, R., Wiborg Schneider, J., 2009. How to use Bibexcel for various types of bibliometric analysis, in: Åström, F., Danell, R., Larsen, B., Schneider, J. (Eds.), *Celebrating Scholarly Communication Studies: A Festschrift for Olle Persson at His 60th Birthday*. International Society for Scientometrics and Infometrics, Leuven, pp. 9–24.
- [25] Porter, A.L., Cunningham, S.W., 2005. *Tech mining: exploiting new technologies for competitive advantage*. John Wiley & Sons Inc., Hoboken, NJ.
- [26] Tur-Porcar, A., Mas-Tur, A., Merigó, J.M., Roig-Tierno, N., Watt, J. 2018. A bibliometric history of the Journal of Psychology between 1936 and 2015. *Journal of Psychology* 152, 199-225.
- [27] Valenzuela, L., Merigó, J.M., Johnston, W., Nicolás, C., Jaramillo, F. 2017. Thirty years of the Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing: A bibliometric analysis, *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing* 32, 1-18.
- [28] Blanco-Mesa, F., Merigó, J.M., Gil-Lafuente, A.M. 2017. Fuzzy decision making: A bibliometric-based review. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems* 32, 2033–2050.
- [29] Martínez-López, F.J., Merigó, J.M., Valenzuela, L., Nicolás, C. 2018. Fifty years of the European Journal of Marketing: A bibliometric analysis. *European Journal of Marketing* 52(1-2), 439–468.
- [30] Peters, H.P.F., van Raan, A.F., 1991. Structuring scientific activities by co-author analysis: An exercise on a university faculty level. *Scientometrics* 20, 235–255.
- [31] Callon, M., Courtial, J.P., Turner, W.A., Bauin, S., 1983. From translations to problematic networks: An introduction to co-word analysis. *Social Science Information* 22, 191–235.
- [32] Mulet-Forteza, C., Martorell-Cunill, O., Merigó, J.M., Genovart-Balaguer, J., Mauleon-Mendez, E. 2018. Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing: A bibliometric analysis, *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing* 35, 1201-1221.
- [33] Wang, W., Laengle, S., Merigó, J.M., Yu, D., Herrera-Viedma, E., Cobo, M.J., Bouchon-Meunier, B. 2018. A bibliometric analysis of the first twenty-five years of the International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems. *International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems* 26, 169–193.
- [34] Huang, Y., Zhu, D., Lv, Q., Porter, A.L., Robinson, D.K.R., Wang, X., 2017. Early insights on the Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI): an overlay map-based bibliometric study. *Scientometrics* 111, 2041–2057.
- [35] Gutiérrez-Salcedo, M., Angeles Martínez, M., Moral-Munoz, J., Herrera-Viedma, E., Cobo, M., 2018. Some bibliometric procedures for analyzing and evaluating research fields. *Applied Intelligence* 48, 1275–1287.
- [36] Cancino, C.A., Merigó, J.M., Coronado, F.C., 2017. A bibliometric analysis of leading universities in innovation research. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge* 2, 106–124.
- [37] Laengle, S., Merigó, J.M., Miranda, J., Słowinski, R., Bomze, I., Borgonovo, E., Dyson, R.G., Oliveira, J.F., Teunter, R., 2017. Forty years of the European Journal of Operational Research: A bibliometric overview. *European Journal of Operational Research* 262, 803–816.
- [38] Van Eck, N.J., Waltman, L., 2014. Visualizing Bibliometric Networks, in: Ding, Y., Rousseau, R., Wolfram, D. (Eds.), *Measuring Scholarly Impact: Methods and Practice*. Springer, pp. 285–320.

Hugo Baier-Fuentes

Hugo Baier-Fuentes is a PhD in Business by the University of Barcelona (Spain). Currently he is an Assistant Professor and Academic Director MBA at the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration at the Universidad Católica de la Santísima Concepción, Chile. He also holds a Bachelor in Industrial Engineering from the Adventist University of Chile. He has published in several international journals including *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, *European Journal of International Management* and *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*. His research includes the study of bibliometrics, international entrepreneurship and the international strategy of Latin American small firms. His works have been presented in the leading conferences of Spain, including Spanish Academy of Management (ACEDE), and the Academy of International Business Conference.

Jesús-Daniel Cascón-Katchadourian

Jesús-Daniel Cascón-Katchadourian is PhD in Documentation Studies and Master in Documentation and Scientific Communication. He has a degree in History and another in Documentation from the University of Granada. He received the first national award by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport. His interest areas are related with cartography, georeferencing and geolocation of historical photography, bibliometric studies and information retrieval. He currently enjoys a postdoctoral contract at the University of Granada.

María-Ángeles Martínez-Sánchez

María-Ángeles Martínez-Sánchez is a PhD in Social Sciences, Master in Information and Scientific Communication, and graduate in Social Work from the University of Granada. She is an Associate professor in the Department of Social Work and Social Services. Her most recent research revolves around science analysis, bibliometric studies, digital libraries, and social services. She is author of 10 JCR publications and different international conference contributions.

Enrique Herrera-Viedma

Enrique Herrera-Viedma is Professor in Computer Science and A.I in University of Granada and currently the new Vice-President for Research and Knowledge Transfer and Vice-President for Publications in IEEE SMC Society. His current research interests include group decision making, consensus models, linguistic preference modeling, aggregation of information, information retrieval, bibliometrics, digital libraries, web quality evaluation, recommender systems, social networks, and social media. In these topics he has published more than 250 papers in JCR journals and coordinated more than 20 research projects. Dr. Herrera-Viedma is member of the government board of the IEEE SMC Society and an Associate Editor of several international journals such as the *IEEE Trans. On Syst. Man, and Cyb.: Systems, IEEE Trans. On Fuzzy Systems, Knowledge Based Systems, Soft Computing, Fuzzy Optimization and Decision Making, Applied Soft Computing, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems, and Information Sciences*. Since 2014 he has been selected as a Highly Cited Author in both categories Computer Science and Engineering by Clarivate Analytics.